

4) Методик, которые позволят вам в совершенстве выучить иностранный язык за два-три месяца не существует. Изучение языка – продолжительный и трудоемкий процесс.

5) Профессионализм преподавателя имеет большее значение, чем методика обучения, которая заявлена в школе, поскольку вывеска не всегда соответствует содержанию.

Таким образом, теоретический анализ и практический опыт показывают, что изучение РКИ учащимися школ находится в спектре актуальных задач психолого-педагогических и филологических наук в плане ее развития и формирования.

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TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE (TEFL). EFFECTIVE LEARNERS AND A LEARNER-CENTERED CLASSROOM

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Annotation. This thesis will give a clear definition about designing effective learning atmosphere for the learners, how a facilitator can avoid some old teaching stereotypes and realize a real Learner- Centered Classrooms.

Key words. Methods, teaching process, learning environment, visualization, classroom tools, active learning, visual aids, learner, requirements, flexibility, challenges, group work, self-assessment, diagrams, cumulative process

Designing effective learning requirements requires a clear understanding of, and attention to, both commonalities and differences in the learners and the learning. Each learner and each learning experience is unique; yet educators can identify patterns in the learning process. Designing effective learning requirements requires a clear understanding of, and attention to, both commonalities and differences in the learners and the learning. Since ancient times, the learning process has been a subject of study for philosophers, educators, and scientists. This curiosity continues to drive forward the methodologies used in a classroom. One major change in educational philosophy brought on by this research is the shift in paradigm from a teacher-centered classroom to a learner-centered classroom. This shift makes the students (learners) more responsible for their education, forcing them to draw upon previously learned skills in order to learn new material. The simple task of memorization can be easily replaced with an active, educational process. How does a teacher create a learner-centered classroom? Here we can mention several suggestions, so teacher can not only create a learner-centered classroom, but also shift his/her classroom position from simple lecturer to a knowledge facilitator:

Link new information to prior knowledge. Meaningful and lasting learning is a cumulative process that connects previously learned material with new knowledge. Background knowledge creates a context and foundation for new material. Unsuccessful students often do not have the skills for linking previous learning to new information. They often lack essential retrieval strategies. Prior knowledge and experience remains inaccessible for these students. The instructional challenge is to help students get in touch with what they already know. Learners need a repertoire of strategies to help them access this knowledge, as well as strategies for organizing new information into patterns that will help them make connections and integrate new understandings. Visualizations of past

learning experiences. It can be organized by Quick (five minute) reviews, Brainstorming and groupin, Venn Diagrams, Semantic mapping, Group or class discussions.⁷⁶Engage with process and context simultaneously. Motivating students' mental engagement is critical to successful education. Engaging instruction is student-centered, designed to instill a sense of wonderment, build self-esteem, and foster creativity. Open-ended experiences, with no "right or wrong" answers allow students to practice generating alternatives to simple memorization of facts, and choose actions and answers based on judgment and not just what they think the teacher wants to hear. In this way, context comes alive as knowledge and skills are applied in context actively and interactively. When students are given a choice in the when, what, and how of learning, they are more likely to embrace learning goals and increase their commitment to learning tasks. This idea is particularly important to students who feel they have little control over many aspects of their lives. Teachers who provide flexibility will most often get a higher level of responsibility from their students. In this position we can see some challenges, such as: Choices in assignment time frames, various levels of difficulty for assignments, different formats for final products, different methods for task completion, options for either individual or peer work. The ability to organize information is fundamental to effective thinking and learning. Skilled learners are able to organize information by recognizing and developing patterns . Learning-focused teachers move from isolated skills lessons to learning strategies lessons, sending the message to students that information gains value when we understand it and apply it. In this way, students gain a tool kit for building, shaping, and connecting information.⁷⁷ Teaching students various organizational tools (along with constantly modeling them) provides cues for thinking, frameworks for accessing and retaining information, and the transfer of learning to other settings. This tool kit can contain:Venn diagrams, story maps, concept maps, graphically displayed patterns and connections, sequence chart. In a meditative learning

⁷⁶ Fundamental Research. Penza: Publishing House "The Academy of Natural Sciences", 11-5: 1135-1139

⁷⁷ Kutbiddinova R.A., 2015. Activation of educational activity of students through interactive methods. Bulletin of the University, 3: 210-214.

environment, open-ended questions are the norm and both praise and criticism are limited. Students are encouraged to articulate “thinking in progress” as they experiment with both ideas and materials. The goal here is to transfer the external meditative voice of the teacher to the inner voice of the student. This self-talk and student-to-student talk guides the work on topics at hand and provides ways of focusing on and thinking about the materials at hand. Meditative teachers and their learners mutually develop challenging goals and criteria for success for units and projects. Reflection and self-assessment along the way are critical components of such classrooms. The concept of learning and teaching has come a long way itself. So, teachers need to take a proactive hand in aiding and developing the learning process as well as teaching students how to learn. In order to acquire language, learners need a source of natural communication. Unfortunately, with adult students, a quick look at current methodologies clearly shows that communication is set aside, neglected or even disregarded. According to linguists, there is an important distinction between language acquisition and language learning. Children acquire their mother tongue through interaction with their parents and the environment that surrounds them. Their need to communicate paves the way for language acquisition to take place. As experts suggest, there is an innate capacity in every human being to acquire language. By the time a child is five years old, s/he can express ideas clearly and almost perfectly from the point of view of language and grammar. Although parents never sit with children to explain to them the workings of the language, their utterances show a superb command of intricate rules and patterns that would drive an adult crazy if s/he tried to memorize them and use them accurately. This suggests that it is through exposure to the language and meaningful communication that a first language is acquired, without the need of systematic studies of any kind. When it comes to second language learning in children, this happens almost identically to their first language acquisition. And even teachers focus more on the communicative aspect of the language rather than on just rules and patterns for the children to repeat and memorize.

In short, we see this tendency in which second language teachers are quite aware of the importance of communication in young learners and their inability to memorize rules consciously (although they will definitely acquire them through a hands-on approach just as they did with their mother tongue). Unfortunately, when it comes to adult students, a quick look at the current methodologies and language courses available clearly shows that communication is set aside, neglected or even disregarded. In almost all cases, courses revolve around grammar, patterns, repetitions, drillings and rote memorization without even a human interlocutor to interact with. Language without real communication is as useless as Saint Valentine's day without lovers or Children's day without kids. The work done in class is mostly grammatically oriented: tenses, rules, multiple choice exercises and so on and so forth. Is this similar to the way in which a child "acquires a language?" Definitely not. No wonder why so many people fail in acquiring a second language naturally. Simply because whatever they are doing is highly unnatural and devoid of meaning to them. This is the field of language learning. Language learning as seen today is not communicative. It is the result of direct instruction in the rules of language. And it certainly is not an age-appropriate activity for your young learners – as it is not for adults either. In language learning, students have conscious knowledge of the new language and can talk about that knowledge. As teachers, it is our duty to make sure that our students "acquire" rather than "learn" the language

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ЛИНГВОДИДАКТИКА И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОД ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

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Аннотация. В статье обосновывается важность обучения студентов корейскому языку при помощи различные методы. Сейчас много говорится о